

Aircraft noise exposure and impact assessment and management

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ABSTRACT:

ICAO Balanced Approach for aircraft noise management in airports [1] is completely about noise exposure, - beginning from assessment with noise index L_{dn} and finalising with noise mitigation measures for flights. Current ICAO policy on Environmental Protection defines the goal concerning noise as a reduction of number of people affected by noise - not simply exposed [2]. If to combine the both assessments - exposure and impact - one may observe at once that current methodology on risk assessment and management may be implemented with a big number of tools and definitions under it [3]. First of all vulnerability effects must be described carefully - a number of acoustic and non-acoustic factors exist, which may or amplify or reduce the impact of noise on people, even for the same noise exposure. A list of factors is different for any of types of impact currently found in practical conditions: annoyance, sleep disturbance, cardiovascular disorders and other direct health effects, cognitive disruptions, mental health, hearing impairment, etc. Annoyance is considered as more general effect, sometimes covering all other types of impact, it is mostly defined via dependence of highly annoyed percentage in population from noise index at their location.

More accurately the exposure is defined - it provides more accurate impact assessment, it is obvious that not only via evident exposure dependence. Vulnerability factors are becoming more accurately defined as well in such case. Principal contributions of vulnerability factors is described in a paper [3]. Improvements in exposure calculations are shown for single events and for day traffic scenario in airports.

1. INTRODUCTION

Till now all the existing ICAO Balanced Approach (BA) elements are subjects to identify and assess the noise exposure only [4], mostly via noise contour modelling, in some cases via instrumental monitoring, which allows to evaluate noise control measures and to determine the most cost-effective and efficient for environment protection set of them [1]. In best known solutions, the process is continuing with public notification

and consultation procedures and even being a mechanism for dispute resolution. This important approach is implemented in the European Environmental Noise Directive. According to it, noise action plans will be developed with the participation of the public. The claim of the citizens in participation has steadily grown, especially if their residential area or essential environmental aspects are concerned.

There was concluded [3] that in parallel to exposure analysis the vulnerability of the population to noise is dominant value for final results of noise impact assessment. In general case vulnerability of the *elements-at-risk* (population living around the airports) to the hazard under consideration (aircraft noise) – “the conditions determined by physical, social, economic and environmental factors or processes, which increase the susceptibility of a community to the impact of hazards” [5], so a term *vulnerability* “describes such characteristics and circumstances of a community, system or asset under consideration that make them susceptible to the damaging effects of a hazard” [5]. Relating to a number of interrelated conditions vulnerability may increase the susceptibility of a community to the impact of any hazards, including noise. In this case the level of noise exposure is considered as the significant determinant of perceived disturbance by residents.

Concept of vulnerability is proposed to be widening to include the coping capacity of the system under consideration, as it is considered by [6] and it takes into account the multifunctional dependent concept-formula between *hazard*, *vulnerability* and *capacity* [7]. In such context, in dependence with conditions and requirements for aircraft noise impact assessment in values of human annoyance to noise the main terms are defined as following: the *intrinsic vulnerability* is a known receptor (human) sensitivity to noise; *human centered experience with ham* (noise annoyance) is a differentiation between the receptor susceptibility to source of noise and other possible vulnerability factors; *dualistic susceptibility/coping capacity* approach defines the changed susceptibility of the receptor to noise impact if any kind of protection measure is realized at a receptor point at the moment of

noise impact assessment; *multiple structure of the vulnerability* to noise annoyance is a balanced approach to noise exposure control (in source, along propagation path, at receptor point); *multi-dimensional vulnerability* is combined exposure control with control of social, economic, environmental and institutional factors of the vulnerability of the elements-at-risk (expose by noise population).

Comparing with traditional ICAO BA elements, which are defined by physical effects of sound generation and propagation, an annoyance is a psychological phenomenon. The type of information collected and the way in which it is analyzed and reported will differ according to the objective of the program of noise control. Usual option of quantifying overall noise exposure – through noise contour modelling and quantifying the number of people inside the contour with specified noise level. Efforts to reduce exposure should primarily reduce annoyance and sleep disturbance, improve learning conditions for children and lower the prevalence of cardiovascular risk factors and cardiovascular disease [8] – they usually have different coping capacities for all these types of health consequences. Evidence is increasing to support preventive measures separately to them, such as noise insulation, policy, guidelines and limit values.

2. VULNERABILITY TO NOISE ADJUSTMENTS

It was found that human response to noise is varying differently among environmental sound sources that are observed to have the same acoustic levels. Vulnerability of the people to type of transportation noise is different due to a number of reasons, described elsewhere [9, 10]. Percentage of highly annoyed (HA) people in dependence from day-night average sound level L_{DN} for three modes of transportation is a classical picture of different *population vulnerability to the type of transportation noise source* – it is the highest for aviation in comparison with road and railway noise effects. For the level $L_{DN} = 65$ dBA (a limit proposed to be used for prohibition of residential area in airports vicinity), the percentage of HA people under the aircraft noise is expected to be 30%, while for railway noise it is equal to 12% only, so the noise exposure level is the same, but damage for population (their annoyance) is assessed as two to three times higher. For this reason, the standard ISO 1996-1:2003 [11] recommends 3–6 dB penalties and bonuses (or simply adjustments) for aircraft and train noise, respectively. Moreover, the noise response curves, which were defined from surveys in various noisy environments, are changed dramatically during the last decades, becoming

more “annoying” in comparison with their first definitions [12], it may be concluded that exposure levels are still the same, never mind that transport traffic grew sufficiently, but vulnerability effects are changed huge (community expectations first of all).

Due to these and other differences, ISO 1996-1 [11] provides and describes a number of adjustments for sounds that have different characteristics. The term “rating level” is used to describe physical sound predictions to which these adjustments may have been added. On the basis of such rating levels, the long-term community response can be estimated, for example, an Equation D.1 in ISO 1996-1 [11] is the original Schultz interpolation curve, showing the portion of a community that may be assessed as highly annoyed by transportation noise sources in dependence to the long-term (up to the year averaging) day-night sound level L_{DN} . Taking this in mind, it may be proposed to be considered as a normalized value of noise annoyance in population L_{DNISO} , so any particular type of environmental noise (any type of transportation, or building construction, or wind turbine noise, etc.) L_{DNs} should be assessed using specific noise source adjustment ΔL_s , which is character for environmental noise under consideration:

$$L_{DNs} = L_{DNISO} + \Delta L_s. \quad (1)$$

Type of noise source is not a single acoustic factor of the vulnerability. Spectral composition of noise produced by the source is the second important acoustic factor as for vulnerability, as for exposure analysis, and number of others [13-15]. The extent of noise annoyance is clearly influenced by numerous non-acoustic factors such as personal, attitudinal and situational in addition to the amount of noise exposure per se [13]. Different models have been developed that aim to provide insight into the processes that result in noise annoyance [9, 10]. However, all these models are developed based on empirical evidence related to previously found results of correlation analysis or multiple regression analysis between noise annoyance and other variables. Both these methods have severe deficiencies in modelling noise annoyance; even the direction of causation may remain uncertain. The results of correlation analysis can be misinterpreted since the effect of the factor under investigation is not controlled for noise exposure or other factors [14]. Also, in [10] it was noted that “many of the models which are tested by using path analysis are exploratory. As such, they probably do not adequately represent the processes leading to the outcome in question e.g., noise annoyance”.

Community response against aviation noise is closely related to perception, attitudes and

expectations of the population under the impact of this noise as it follows (Table 3.5 in [3]). The most important determinants of any of the factors (variable) are shown also, so as their effect on noise annoyance as well (the data for standardized total effects of each variable are taken mostly from [14]). Vader in [15] compiled an array of 31 non-acoustic factors and classified each of them according to two dimensions: its *influence* on annoyance (strong, intermediate, weak – also shown in Table 3.5 in 3]) and the possibility to be modified.

In an attempt to reduce the scatter to the community response data, the EPA [12] suggested the use of “normalized” L_{DN} , which is the measured or predicted L_{DN} with a number of *adjustments* like in Equation (1) added to account for specific characteristics of the sound [17]: *seasonal considerations* – summer (or year-round operation) $\Delta L=0$ dB, winter only (or windows always closed) $\Delta L=-5$ dB; *outdoor background noise* measured in the absence of intruding noise – quiet suburban or rural community (remote from large cities and from industrial activity and trucking) $\Delta L=10$ dB, normal suburban community (not located near an industrial activity) $\Delta L=5$ dB, urban residential community (not immediately adjacent to heavily travelled roads or industrial areas) $\Delta L=0$ dB, noisy urban residential community (near relatively busy roads or industrial areas) $\Delta L=-5$ dB, very noisy urban residential community $\Delta L=-10$ dB; *change in noise environment and community attitudes* – community has had some previous exposure to the intruding noise, but little effort is being made to control the noise $\Delta L=0$ dB, community has had considerable previous exposure to the intruding noise, and the noisemaker’s relations with the community are good $\Delta L=-5$ dB, community is aware that the operation causing the noise is very necessary and will not continue indefinitely $\Delta L=-10$ dB, etc. All of them in proposed above risk terminology are *vulnerability factors* for the risk to be annoyed by noise assessment also. For new situations, especially when the community is not familiar with the sound source in question, greater community annoyance than predicted by application of the equation can be expected, the difference may be as much as +5 dB. One more classical example of noise impact vulnerability is additional guideline values, which are suggested for specific environments [18].

3. EXPECTATION RATE TO NOISE ADJUSTMENTS

Looking in Equation (1) and considering the noise annoyance effect, it was proposed to represent the likelihood of the consequences (effect or damage) $P_{d/f}$ in individual risk calculation [3] for noise impact as a dependence of $HA\%$ from noise metric L_{DN} (or

its analogue L_{DEN}), currently it should be noted that normalized dependence is considered. A vulnerability shift in relation to noise source (ΔL_s) is proposed to be included in a form of adjustment used in [11] – Eq. (1). Today it is highest for noise from wind turbines, because expectation rate among the population in quiet suburban or rural community, where wind farms are usually installed, is highest. Such expectation rate is introduced to assess the expected vulnerability effect on a value of response of the population on noise via the factor of expectation (Fig. 1):

$$\Delta L_{s i} = \Delta L_{s i \max} F_{ex}, \quad (2)$$

where i is a type of vulnerability considered and $\Delta L_{s i \max}$ is a maximum possible value of vulnerability shift.

Figure 1. Factor of expectation (expectation factor $F_{ex} = [0, 1]$) in dependence with rate of expectation $R_{ex} = [0, 100]$: any deviation from the expected level in the direction of growth causes the growth F_{ex} .

A form of the factor of expectation may be different for different vulnerability aspects, but expected to be similar with one of dose-effect curves for various types of response to hazard (Fig. 2), usually used for quantal response of the recipient to dose of toxicant (reflecting a given exposure of chemical or biological stressor).

Further step is a “normalization” procedure for noise level used in noise impact assessment:

$$L_{DN \text{ norm}} = L_{DN \text{ cal/meas}} + \Delta L_{s \Sigma} \quad (3)$$

where calculated or measured value $L_{DN \text{ cal/meas}}$ is correspondent with case of noise event under consideration, and vulnerability shift $\Delta L_{s \Sigma}$ may include additively a number of factors influencing on vulnerability of the receptor to noise in this case.

4. MAIN PRINCIPLES REALIZED IN CURRENT METHODOLOGY OF AIRCRAFT NOISE CALCULATION

ICAO calculation method [19] may be accompanied with EU analogue [20], taking in mind small but essential differences between them. Both methods are grounded on requirements of

the standard for aircraft noise calculations [21]. The methodology applies to long-term average noise exposure only, "... it cannot be relied upon to predict with any accuracy the absolute level of noise from a single aeroplane movement and should not be used for that purpose" [19]. Current versions of appropriate software (INM, SONDEO, ANCON, IsoBella, etc) are fully correspondent with these recommendations. But a number of national noise regulation rules require for single noise event control or via L_{Amax} , or SEL , or any other noise descriptor, which is correspondent with noise event, particularly with aircraft noise event.

Figure 2. Dose-effect curves for various types of response to hazard: NOAEL, no-observed-adverse-effect level

Noise data in most current integrated model their data base are generally supplied by the aircraft manufacturers in form of Noise-Power-Distance (NPD) curves, which are fixed to standard temperature and humidity. As a simulation model, its acoustical basis consists of point sources, which move dynamically in time. It accounts for geometric spreading, air absorption and ground effect. Both models represent the same physical phenomena, but do so with different levels of detail and some different choices in particular algorithms. Flight profiles are defined by software via solutions of balanced motion equations, which are recommended by existing methods [19-21], using the data for necessary coefficients from ANP database, which is supported by Eurocontrol (aircraftnoisemodel.com).

The noise at points on the ground from aeroplanes flying into and out of a nearby aerodrome depends on many factors. Principal among these are the types of aeroplanes and their powerplants; the power, flap and airspeed management procedures used on the aeroplanes themselves; the distances from the points concerned to the various flight paths; and local topography and weather. Airport operations generally include different types of aeroplanes, various flight procedures and a range of operational masses. Determining the event level for a single aircraft movement at a single observer point is the core calculation. The documents [19-21] detail how to calculate, at one observer point, the individual aeroplane noise event levels, each for a specific aeroplane flight or type of flight, that

are subsequently averaged, or accumulated, to yield index values at that point. The required surface of index values is generated by repeating the calculations as necessary for different aeroplane movements - taking care to maximize efficiency by excluding events that are not "noise-significant" (i.e. disregarding segments that do not contribute significantly to the total event level yields massive savings in computer processing). The methodology [19-21] applies only to long-term average noise exposure; it cannot be relied upon to predict with any accuracy the absolute level of noise from a single aeroplane movement and should not be used for that purpose.

5. ADEQUACY OF AIRCRAFT NOISE ASSESSMENT AROUND THE AIRPORTS

Today the INM software does not take into account the effect of buildings on sound propagation (effects of line-of-sight blockage of the noise – reflection and shielding). But they are very important for helicopter noise because of their flights over residential/building areas mostly. SAE-AIR-1845A "Procedure for the Calculation of Airplane Noise in the Vicinity of Airports" provides guidance for modeling aircraft noise at airports with flat terrain. In reality, many airports are surrounded by non-level terrain that may result in noise blockage (or shielding) at some nearby receptors. This noise blockage can be accounted for with the line-of-sight blockage calculation, based on the difference in propagation path length between the direct path and propagation path over the top of terrain features. Depending on effect of line-of-sight interaction with surface covering obstacles in comparison with flat terrains the differences in SEL predictions may reach ± 10 dBA ("+" is mostly for case with reflections, "-" is for shielding).

The airport (aerodrome) scheme may prioritize the taxiway noise in comparison with aircraft flight, including the noise from the aircraft on runway – during takeoff and landing. With more successful noise reduction in source such prioritization becomes higher because of less contribution of noise from runway rolls and overflights of the aeroplanes and closer location of taxiways in a number of airports to residential areas. Noise reduction efficiency is much greater at flight modes in comparison with taxi modes providing this taxiway noise prioritization [22].

It is the predicted changes between propagation over ground and water which illustrate a nominal $\Delta SEL = 2$ dBA effect of ground impedance on sound propagation for sources at low elevation angles. Aircraft with fuselage mounted engines are 1.5 dB quieter in the plane of the wing than aircraft with wing mounted engines [23]. In fact, differences between the predicted attenuation effects on overall A-weighted levels L_A can be as much as 12 dBA due to the spectrum variations between aircraft engine types, or even for one type

of the engine, but in various directions (see Fig. 3). The magnitude of the predicted variation is the same, or even greater, as that for NPD variations due to temperature of the air [24].

More spectral dependence is shown in Fig. 4 – the lateral effect was calculated for spectral classes, currently included in ANP data base, covering the departure and arrival flight modes, and three types of engines – turbojets (TJ), turbofans (TF) and turboprops (TP).

Figure 3. Ground Effect as a Function of The Angle of Engine Noise Radiation

Figure 4. Calculated lateral effect for spectral classes, currently included in ANP data base

6. ACCURACY OF AIRCRAFT NOISE ASSESSMENT AROUND THE AIRPORTS

The noise of aircraft, especially jet aircraft equipped with lower bypass ratio engines, exhibits a lobed radiation pattern in the rearward arc, which is characteristic of jet exhaust noise. The start of take-off roll (SOTR) directivity adjustment Δ_{SOR} is not aircraft-specific currently [19,21] and it was based on now out-of-date aircraft fleet data. Latest version of the Doc 29 [20] includes two types of adjustments - for turbofan-powered jet and for turboprop-powered aeroplanes. But the directivity patterns of noise radiation backward are specific to each engine type, Fig. 5. The dispersion of the differences between SEL for specific type of aeroplane/engine is of the same value ± 10 dBA as for effects of line-of-sight interaction.

To improve the accuracy of airport noise calculations it is proposed [24] to provide in model data base few type specific directivity patterns to calculate the aircraft noise, when aircraft is maneuvering on the ground: depending from engine type in power plant of the aircraft (Jet, Turbofan, Turboprop); depending from aircraft group – CIVILIAN (General Aviation and/or Commercial) and/or MILITARY; depending from aircraft weight class: Jumbo Air Carrier, Heavy Air Carrier, Large Air Carrier, Regional Jet, Propeller Aircraft; depending from the spectral class of the aircraft, which is character for aircraft departure and arrival. In [13] there are 5 character directivity adjustment Δ_{SOR} are proposed in accordance with predefined aircraft weight class, described with polynomial expressions inside $0^\circ < \theta < 180^\circ$ hemisphere and proposed even for taxi noise assessment for the same groups of the aeroplanes.

Figure 5. Generalized directivity corrections for characteristic engine types

Although the resulting additional noise energy generated by aircraft on the runway is relatively small in comparison to other phases of flight, both take-off roll and reverse thrust noise can be noticeable features of the noise environment (*reverse thrust* is usually associated with sudden increase in *noise*, which includes more low-

frequency components and changes in directivity patterns of noise radiation) at points close to the runway. It is therefore important that they are modelled with sufficient accuracy [25], simple raise of engine thrust (realized today in calculation tools and ANP data base) is not enough.

Low frequency aircraft noise is a subject of importance not only for rotocrafts, but even for aeroplanes powered with advanced open rotors and turboprops. The low-frequency trade study [26] demonstrated a strong sensitivity to inclusion of low-frequency effects below 50 Hz over the range of distances (0-25000 ft), therefore the rotorcraft should be modeled down to 10 Hz.

Modelling variable aircraft configuration and speed is discussed smoothly in [27]. It is possible to show large amounts of measured noise data in noise contour presentations and compare those with calculated values. Fig.6 presents these results using data for A-320 and B-737-400 aircraft. It shows that the measured contour for the maximum level 75 dB(A) is up to the 4 km longer than the calculated contour! As shown in Fig. 7, flight profiles of real-life operations tend to differ greatly from predictions for balanced motion.

The differences are observed not only for the height-distance, but for the flight speeds and thrust settings, which also contribute significantly to the predicted levels of noise. The same is observed for arrivals also, where the thrust setting is usually higher than in the balanced motion predictions [28]. Appropriate operational thrusts are much less also (right figure), but both of them – speed and thrust – located in safe diapason, these data are the results of pilot operational qualification and may be defined for every airport/airline/aircraft via statistical analysis. During the arrival phase of a flight, the difference between results observed during operations and the balanced data for flight

parameters is 2-3 dBA higher than the maximum levels calculated by models in accordance with current requirements [29].

Figure 6. Comparison of measured and calculated noise contours for A-320 and B-737-400 aircraft in take-off phase

In Fig. 8 (combine from four figures, which are taken from [29]) the data for arrivals are shown. If to look on the flight speed it should be found that operational speeds (blue) vary along glide path and sometimes their values may be below the safety requirements (balanced value in red). In these cases a pilot must operate with thrust, making engine thrust settings higher, to return the speeds to the safe values. It was found that the thrusts may be twice and more higher than the balanced predictions for them.

Defining real atmospheric conditions for aircraft source and propagation data may result in few ways – in noise radiation and in noise propagation adjustments. Recalculation of NPD-data for user-specified non-reference conditions is proposed to fulfill in different ways: in ICAO Doc 9911 [19] it is doing using so called an acoustic impedance adjustment; in Doc 29 [20] it is doing using so called an increment ΔL , which is the difference between the NPDs in the user-specified atmosphere and the reference atmosphere.

Figure 7. Flight profile parameters (a - height via distance, thrust via distance, c – velocity via distance) observed in operation (blue lines) in comparison with balanced prediction (red lines) during departures [29]

Acoustic impedance is defined as the product of the density of air and the speed of sound, and it is a function of temperature, atmospheric pressure, and indirectly altitude. Acoustic impedance adjustment AI_{ADJ} is computed and applied to the NPD data on an observer-by-observer basis, according to the observer altitude, temperature, and pressure. In Fig. 9 adjustment AI_{ADJ} is shown in comparison with noise level radiation adjustment (ΔL_{inTatm} and ΔL_{ATatm}) for 4 types of the engines with different bypass ratio and engine mode control laws in dependence to air temperature – there is obvious that temperature dependent noise power level changes are higher than predefined with acoustic impedance adjustment AI_{ADJ} only.

All the calculations were done with **NoBel** calculation tool from the NAU with necessary analysis and prediction of thermodynamic parameters of the engine operation cycles in dependence to air temperature T_{atm} for the reference distance 1 m from the source. Prediction results were assessed in 1/3-octave band spectra, which were recalculated to L_{in} and L_A , Fig. 10.

Figure 8. Comparison between observed in operation (blue) velocities and thrusts and predicted balanced values (red). For the left figures the unsafe (less than balanced) velocities are connected with overbalanced thrusts (control from pilot to return the velocity into safe diapason) [29]

In practice, for the derivation of noise-power-distance (NPD) data for a range of thrusts (powers) covering full take-off and reduced thrusts (powers) the aeroplane is flown past lateral and under-flight-

path microphones according to either the take-off procedures defined in 3.6.2 and 4.5 of Annex 16, Volume I [30] or, more typically, the flight path intercept procedures described in 2.1.1 of this manual [31].

Figure 9. Comparison of noise power level adjustment (ΔL_{inTatm} and ΔL_{ATatm}) with acoustic impedance adjustment AI_{ADJ} for 4 types of the engines with different bypass ratio and flight control laws: a) $m=1$; b) $m=4$; c) $m=5.7$; d) $m=5.7$ (different from c) engine mode control law)

Target test conditions are established for each sound measurement. These target test conditions define the flight procedure, aerodynamic

configuration to be selected, aeroplane weight, power, airspeed and, at the closest point of approach to the measurement location, height. Pilot should “set up” the aeroplane in the appropriate condition in order to pass by the noise measurement location within the target height window, while maintaining target power and airspeed, within agreed tolerances, throughout the 10dB-down time period.

Figure 10. Assessed spectra, L_{in} and L_A for the engine with bypass ratio 5.7 in dependence to air temperature T_{atm} for the reference distance 1 m

The same principles were used for recalculation of the NPD tables at different air conditions – temperature, pressure and humidity. NPD data for maximum operation thrust mode of the engine ($m=1$) and for 4 character air temperatures are shown in Fig. 11 a) and the differences between them and NPD data for standard atmosphere $T_{atm}=288^{\circ}K$. Atmosphere layer was simplified to uniform (constant parameters along the height of the layer).

It should be noted that explanation presented ahead provides the differences between the NPD data used for uniform atmosphere and for standard atmospheric conditions (or any other conditions in atmosphere layer under consideration), for example as they are defined by the standard [32]. From this point of view the rays of sound propagation are the curves (not straight lines like they are used in methodology [19-21]) – so the sound propagation path is larger and the elevation angle β (or angle of noise incidence ($90^{\circ}-\beta$)) may be larger or smaller depending from atmosphere stratification type.

Figure 11. NPD data for maximum operation thrust mode of the engine ($m=1$) and for 4 character air temperatures (a) and the differences between them and NPD data for standard atmosphere $T_{atm}=288^{\circ}K$ (b)

Lateral displacement from the aircraft ground track ℓ and angle β for the line-of-sight are not representative for *total* lateral adjustment assessment.

7. CONCLUSIONS

It should be a primary objective of future research into environmental noise impact to investigate the interplay of sound level control and perceived control. New and additional (political) measures to mitigate noise impact may result from the redirection of attention from sound to noise and to noise annoyance. Strategies that reduce noise annoyance, as opposed to noise, may be more effective in terms of protecting public health from the adverse impacts of noise and its interdependency with other environmental, operational, economic and organizational issues of airport and airlines operation and maintenance.

The reviewed and proposed models provide a good model fit and support to the toolboxes of noise annoyance management, currently under the design. It can be concluded that the concern about the negative health effects of noise and pollution, other environmental issues, are still the subjects of scientific and societal attention, their newish deliverables may improve the approach to build the fifth element of ICAO balanced approach to aircraft noise control around the airports, which cover the measures to reach the final goal of aircraft noise management – to reduce the number of

people living in vicinity of the airports and affected by noise.

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